

DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION AT THE PRESENT TIME

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Abstract. *The article focuses on the changes in the education system and the role of the human factor in the formation of quality education.*

Key words: *quality education, educational system, examination, methods, conclusions, proposals.*

A positive relationship between education and economic, political, and cultural development is widely assumed throughout much of the modern and modernizing world, yet research suggests that this relationship is problematic. The problem has two aspects. First, although many empirical studies show a positive relationship between many forms of education and individual economic, political, and cultural development, the effects of education on development at the collective level are ambiguous. Second, at the same time evidence of this for ambiguity has been mounting, faith in education as the fulcrum for individual and for collective development has been growing in the form of international education conferences and declarations and national-level education policies.

This chapter explores two aspects of the problem in distinct ways. First, in the sections on the effects of education on development and the effects of development on education, we review the empirical relationship between education and development, drawing on several decades of cross-national studies. Second, in

education and development. These effects include the proliferation and spread of development discourse, development organizations, and development professionals, all of which celebrate and promote expanded visions of education as human capital and as a human right (Chabbott, 1996). These visions have a significant impact on what educational statistics are collected, how development progress is measured, and what education policies nation-states are encouraged to adopt. To reiterate, these two general conclusions constitute an interesting paradox: despite growing scholarly acknowledgment that our understanding of the link between education and development contains many gray areas, public confidence in these links, manifest in national policies and in international declarations, continues to mount. It is this paradox that motivates our review of the literature and our delineation of new research directions in the study of development and education.

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